

FIBRE BREAKINGS DETECTION IN UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITES USING MICROWAVE TECHNOLOGY

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SUMMARY

This article shows how fibre breakings in unidirectionnal composite materials have been detected by using a resonator microstrip that has been excited by microwaves.

Keywords: Microwaves, Nondestructive evaluation, Fiber-reinforced composite material, Damage Detection

INTRODUCTION AND AIM OF THE STUDY

The growth of the use of composite materials in transportation (railways, automobiles, aeronautics) and the enforcement of safety rules necessitates the periodic inspection of their structural integrity. This inspection can give warning of impending fracture due to a loss of mechanical characteristics resulting from damage. A review of the literature shows a number of possible non-destructive techniques to detect damage inside materials or structures. The number of these techniques that are practical for a given inspection is, however, small because of problems of cost, the speed at which a in-situ measurement can be given (to reduce the costs of immobilization) and their applicability to composite materials. Techniques such as infrared thermography, acoustic emissions, EMIR (ElectroMagnetic InfraRed) and microwave imagery lend themselves easily enough to fit our needs. No technique, however, is ideal and each possesses its own advantages and inconveniences. Therefore, we wish to develop a technique that allows us:

- to take measurements easily and in-situ;
- to identify and distinguish between different types of damage;
- to quantify different damages;
- to locate damage present even within the depths of the material.

The aim of this study is to show how fibre breakings in unidirectionnal composite materials have been detected by using a resonator microstrip that has been excited by microwaves. This technique is founded on the observation and the analysis of the modifications of the dielectric properties of a material due to damage. To be precise, its originality lies in the fact that the diagnostic to be found is obtained by the analysis of the response, in the microwave range, of a resonant microstrip circuit. In this article, we limit ourselves to demonstrating the feasibility of the technique. Thus, its ability to detect anisotropy as well as fibre breakings within a unidirectional composite will be demonstrated. Its potential capabilities will be also mentioned. On the other hand, for the instant, it will be not demonstrated whether the proposed technique is capable of quantifying or qualifying a given type of damage.

BIBLIOGRAPHICAL REVIEW

Techniques based on X-ray ([28]...), optic fibre ([32], [21], [33], [10], [20]...), ultra-sound ([27], [3]...), the measurement of electric current ([1], [29]...) are obviously useful for detecting damage in composite materials. However, in the context of this work, it is preferred to use techniques which require less infrastructure. Techniques based on infrared thermography ([5], [18]...) consist in exciting a material by providing energy (mechanical, photonic, heat by induction, lamps, flashes...) and measuring, with the aid of an infrared camera, the resulting temperature increase. These techniques can be applied to composites and, for instance, provide information about the nature of defects, especially if their geometry is characteristic (delamination, for example). Techniques

based on acoustic emission ([31], [23], [13]...) consist of collecting and analyzing acoustic waves emitted by the material itself. These waves are created by internal microdisplacements caused, in our case, by damage phenomena within the composite material (fibre/matrix debonding, intralaminar cracks, fibre breaks, delamination). These techniques are already used in some industrial applications, for example, in order to inspect composite pressure vessels (for buses) ([6], [7], [8]) where the large part of damage phenomena consists of fibre break similar to that in unidirectional composite. This last observation is important because, despite a number of studies, both completed and continuing, it has still yet to be shown with certainty that this technique can distinguish one type of damage from another in the cases where several degradations are simultaneously present in the material (intralaminar cracks, fibre breakings, for example). It also remains to be shown whether this technique can finely locate the degradations in the thickness of a material. EMIR (ElectroMagnetic InfraRed) techniques ([4], [22]...) use an antenna or a wave guide that emits a microwave electromagnetic field upon the structure to be tested. The passage of the wave through the material modifies its frequency. A thin absorbent film placed on the opposite end of the material from the antenna transforms the electromagnetic energy into heat which is, in turn, detected by an infrared camera. The frames obtained with this technique can be difficult to read, especially in the depth of the material. Other techniques that use laser interferometry ([19]...) or piezo-electric sensors ([34]...) can also be mentioned. Finally, two large families of techniques use electromagnetic waves in the microwave range. The distinction between these two lies in the fact that one works with contact and the other without. Techniques operating without contact use two antennae, one emitting and the other receiving microwave electromagnetic fields. The material (or the structure) to be examined is placed between the two antennae. The field emitted traverses the material and the transmitted wave is captured and analysed by an receiving antenna ([26]...). The most often used techniques relying on contact, place the material to be examined either at the extreme end of a wave guide or within a coaxial propagating structure in which it plays the role of insulation. A vectorial network analyzer thus characterises the material, by analysing the reflection and the transmission of electromagnetic microwaves through the material ([30], [2], [15], [16], [11], [14], [17]...). In both cases, these techniques do not easily allow the examination of a voluminous structure with complex shapes.

DESCRIPTION OF THE TECHNIQUE

Thus, the above-mentioned techniques cannot be used in the framework required. The microwave technique is however interesting albeit used in a modified fashion. In the domain of telecommunications in the range of microwave frequency, the lines of transmission (excepting open space) are generally either wave guides or microstrip circuits (or "microstrips"). The dielectric properties of the material that constitute the part of the microstrip called "the substrat" has a great influence on the characteristics of the microstrips. The basics of the technique here-in proposed is to use the material in which the damage will be detected, as the substrat of a resonant microstrip circuit. The dielectric properties of the material/substrat are modified by the presence of damage and, as a result, the values of the characteristics properties of the microstrip will vary well, thus revealing the presence of damage in the material/substrate.

The microstrip resonator circuit: basics, definition and measurements of characteristics properties. A microstrip circuit is composed (figure 1) of a insulation substrat metalized on one of its faces (in our case, by a copper film placed there) which plays the role of ground plan. The other face is partially covered by metal in the form of a small conductive ribbon. A microstrip circuit is a propagation line for an electromagnetic wave. The study of the propagation of an electromagnetic field in a microstrip circuit is difficult because the wave propagates in both the substrat and the air at the same time. Some legitimate hypotheses are, however, in general use:

- the dominant mode of field propagation is Transverse Electromagnetic;
- materials used as substrat have little dielectric loss.

The above hypotheses will be adopted for this study. The shape of the conductive ribbon, for the range of frequencies used, gives the circuit an elementary electronic function, either as filter or as

resonator. In the cases where the circuit is resonant, it is characterized by a resonance frequency, noted f_c , a characteristic impedance, noted Z_c , as well as by a quality factor Q . To demonstrate the feasibility of the proposed method, here, Z_c and Q are not the most important quantities. For this reason, they will be no longer in the following. The measurement of f_c will be obtained in an indirect way. A vectorial network analyzer is connected by a coaxial cable to one of the ends of the conductive ribbon (called "the input"). The other end of the conductive ribbon is connected to a given, fixed impedance Z_{charge} . The reference plan of the measures is the input of the conductive ribbon. In this plan, the analyzer measures the incident electromagnetic waves that it emits. It also measures the reflected wave for which it will be defined a complex reflection coefficient usually called S_{11} , here notated as Γ . The analysis of the measures of Γ versus the frequency of the incidental electromagnetic wave gives f_c . In terms of the hypotheses given, which allow for the simplification of the problem of wave propagation within the circuit, it is possible to calculate Γ and f_c . For the more simple geometries, analytical formulas are available and based on the model of Hammerstadt [12]. For complex geometries, the Maxwell equations need to be solved using numerical techniques. The quantities Γ and f_c depend on the geometry of the conductive ribbon and the substrat. They also depend on the physical properties of their constitutive materials, notably the relative dielectric permittivity ϵ_r of the constitutive material of the substrat. With all of these quantities being fixed ϵ_r and f_c depend only on the frequency of the wave that travels the circuit. For ϵ_r , the dependence is extremely weak for the materials studied here. Thus, it will be implicitly assumed in the following that the permittivity of the material used as substrat is constant.

The technique. The principal objective here is to detect damage in a composite material. For that reason, and for the purposes of the technique presented here, the role of the substrat in the microstrip circuit will be played by the material to inspect. This inspection will be made around the following postulates:

- no dissipative phenomena other than the damage to detect is present in the tested material and the geometric characteristics of the different elements in the circuit remain constant, as do the physical properties of the constitutive materials of ground plan and the conductive ribbon;
- therefore, if variations in the value of Γ and f_c appear over time, these variations will be attributed to variations in the dielectric properties of the constitutive materials of the substrat resulting from damage.

For this, the Small Perturbations Hypothesis was carried out. This hypothesis allows the assumption that any variations in the conductive ribbon are sufficiently small and will fail to modify the characteristics of the microstrip. It will be also considered that, except for the damage to be detected, no other dissipative phenomena (viscosity, irreversible deformation) which might modify the mechanical or dielectric properties of the medium is present. These hypotheses can obviously be falsified close of the breaking state. The method consists, then, in measuring Γ and f_c at different moments, at one or more given frequencies. Then, for each measurement point, ϵ_r is evaluated by using either a analytical or a numerical model in an inverse process: a homogenous substrat equivalent to the damaged substrat is taken and the value of its relative permittivity ϵ_r is adjusted until Γ and f_c coincide with the measured values.

DETECTION OF ANISOTROPY IN A UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITE MATERIAL

Here, it will be revealed whether the technique is able to detect anisotropy in an undamaged composite. In order to do this, two resonant microstrip circuits with identical geometries and substrats were used: one square specimen composed of unidirectional glass/epoxy composite, with 50 mm sides and a thickness of 4 mm. Their difference lay in the position of the ribbon: for one, it was aligned with the composite fibres (called "type 0°") and for the other it was placed perpendicularly (called "type 90°"). The measurements were taken at 2 GHz. It was ascertained that the reflection coefficient Γ was not null and different in each of the two circuits. Then, it could be observed that the resonance frequency was different in each of the two circuits (figure 2).

Therefore, it can be concluded that the proposed technique detects the anisotropy of the material. Some identical measurements using microwaves propagated within open guide have been performed ([9]) on similar materials. These confirm the anisotropic character of the dielectric properties of these materials.

DETECTION OF FIBRE FAILURES IN A UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITE MATERIAL

In order to detect fibre breaks within a given unidirectional composite material, the following procedure was used:

- one flexural test on a unidirectional composite specimen allowed the appearance of fibre breaks to be examined. By observing the variation of the slope of the load/displacement curve, it became possible to detect the damage;
- the specimen used was the substrat of a resonant microstrip circuit for which Γ was measured as a function of time.

Description of the 3-point bending test. The laboratory reference frame is the $R = (O, \vec{x}, \vec{y}, \vec{z})$ (figure 3), the basis of which is noted as B . The specimen was composed of a glass/epoxy unidirectional composite (the mechanical and rupture properties of which are known). The basis of the frame of anisotropy of the material is $B_{mat} = (\vec{X}_1, \vec{X}_2, \vec{X}_3)$: the axis oriented along the vector \vec{X}_1 designates the axis of the fibre, the plan on which the fibres are situated is the plan (\vec{X}_1, \vec{X}_2) . The basis of the specimen frame is $B_{spe} = (\vec{e}_1, \vec{e}_2, \vec{e}_3)$ (figure 4). For all performed experiments, B , B_{mat} and B_{spe} are identical. The specimen length (vector \vec{e}_1) was 150 mm, its width (vector \vec{e}_2) was 48.5 mm and its thickness (vector \vec{e}_3) was 4.5 mm. The specimen is placed upon two parallel cylindrical supports. The axes of the supports are represented by vector \vec{y} . Their diameter was 10 mm and there was 100 mm distance between the two. A cylindrical knife (of 10 mm diameter and 50 mm length), parallel to the supports, applied a vertical, descending sollicitation $-F(t)\vec{z}$ upon the upper face of the specimen. The knife's displacement was noted as $-D(t)\vec{z}$. If the measurements of the characteristic properties of a circuit can, in principle, be taken of any frequency, in this case it was at resonance, those taken at the neighborhood of f_c allow the amplification of the observed variations. In other words, the reason for choosing a resonant circuit in this case can be found in the fact that all permittivity variations of the substrat that are due to damage, when detected at the resonance frequency, will be amplified by the circuit's response. Also, the dimensions of the ribbon have been calculated (with the aid of Hammerstadt's model and by giving an order to the material's permittivity found in the literature) in such a manner that its resonance frequency is close to that of the center of the frequency range of the chosen network analyzer (1.7 GHz). The upper side of the specimen was the loaded surface. Then, the circuit's conductive ribbon was bonded to the inferior surface of the specimen-substrate and the ground plan (a thin cooper film with a thickness of 30 μm) bonded to the upper side (figure 4). Measurements taken of the unload specimen allowed for the verification of our calculations. A first set of tests was used for the calibration of the testing machine and the measurement apparatus. Following this, two tests were undertaken, each giving identical measurements. The tests impose the knife's displacement with a constant speed of 2 mm/mn. Two types of knife's displacement versus time were used:

- for the calibration tests, application of monotonic displacement ranging from nul-value to the value provoking the specimen's rupture;
- for the following two tests, application of a displacement profile of loading/unloading type, the value of the maximum displacement being successively augmented until failure was achieved, the unloading always brings back the knife's displacement to a nul-value (figure 5).

The load applied to the knife will be carried with the help of a loading sensor. Thus the load (F, unit : N)/ imposed displacement (D, unit : mm) curve could be obtained (figure 6). Using the network analyzer the amplitude, the real and the imaginary parts of Γ at the maximum attained displacement values (figure 5, points $(B_i)_{i=1,\dots,5}$) as well as the return to null-value were measured

(figure 5, points $(A_i)_{i=1,\dots,5}$). For each of these points, the test was stopped for a few moments in order to take the measurements of a frequency sweep ranging from 300 KHz to 3 GHz in steps of 15 MHz.

Analysis of mechanical measurements. In order to analyze and confirm the mechanical measurements, a finite element model of the flexural test has been developed. The objective of this calculation was to obtain the vertical displacement and to predict the beginning of the fiber breaking phenomenon. The elements used are quadratic (C3D20). The behavior of the composite material was assumed to be linear and transversely isotropic. A fibre breaking criterion was used with the following form: $c = \text{axial strain} / \text{critical axial strain}$, if $c = 1$, the fibre is broken. Experimentally, the value of the load at which the fall of the slope of the curve load / applied displacement became significant was 2 500 N (figure 6). For this value, the knife's displacement is close to 4.5 mm. Numerically, these values have been confirmed. Also, it is important to point out that in the absence of load, no significant residual displacement was visible except after the application of a maximum displacement superior to 8 mm. Thus, below this value, and especially around 4.5 mm, no dissipative phenomenon was present within the specimen other than the fibre failures. It can be thus concluded that, for a knife's displacement value around 4.5 mm, the fibre failure phenomenon is near to initiation, but has already significantly begun. The microwave measurements associated with the microstrip circuit must, then, demonstrate this.

Analysis of the microwave measurements and their correlation with fibre breaks. The existence of a stress field within the material influences its dielectric properties ([26]). Here, the phenomenon was revealed by measuring the amplitude of Γ when the specimen was both loaded and unloaded (figure 7). Thus, when some measurements taken under charge show variations in the material's properties or microstrip's responses, it is not possible to distinguish, in these variations, that part which is due to the existence of a stress field from that which is truly caused by another phenomenon, notably damage. This is the reason for the second type of applied displacement (load/unload, figure 5). Its interest is, firstly, to confirm the measurements made during the monotonic loading and next to measure the characteristics properties of the microstrip when the knife's displacement has a null-value. We observe the variation of Γ (amplitude, real and imaginary part) relative to the reference state. The analysis of these experimental data shows that the more significant variation, traducing the change of the electrical characteristics of the resonant microstrip line, are those of the imaginary part of $\frac{\Gamma - \Gamma_{ref}}{\Gamma_{ref}}$, where Γ_{ref} is the value of the coefficient Γ measured when the knife's displacement is back to zero after to be going at 1 mm. It will be observed that this coefficient exhibits important variations on and after a knife's displacement of 4.5 mm (figure 8). Remind that this value is those that indicates experimentally and numerically the beginning of the fibre breaking phenomenon. The technique has then detected the presence of damage.

CONCLUSION

This work has not been presented in order to respond to each and every legitimate question associated with the development of a new technique for non-destructive damage detection within composite materials. The goals herein are, firstly, to demonstrate the feasibility of a process is founded on the analysis of the response of a resonator microstrip line in microwave frequency where the material plays the role of substrat. Secondly, it indicates that this method has a number of serious potential advantages as an alternative and complement to current techniques. This technique's feasibility has been demonstrated for unidirectional composite materials and, more precisely, for the detection of anisotropy and fiber ruptures in a probe submitted to flexion. These encouraging first results must now be complemented by learning whether this method is capable of distinguishing the presence of multiple damages and quantifying them. For now, the technique is used to detect delamination (Rossignol and Thionnet, [24], [25]).

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Figure 1: Microstrip principle (A : substrat, B : conductive ribbon, C : ground plan, D : load Z_{charge} , E : coaxial cable, F : network analyzer, G : measurement acquisition)

Figure 2: Amplitude of the coefficient Γ (Amp(Γ), unit : dB) versus frequency (F, unit : GHz); o : microstrip "type 0°", + : microstrip "type 90°"

Figure 3: Flexural apparatus

Figure 4: Tested specimen

Figure 5: Applied displacement (D, unit : mm) versus time (t, unit : s)

Figure 6: Experimental load (F, unit : N)/maximum displacement reached (D, unit : mm) at the points $((B_i)_{i=1,\dots,5})$ (figure 5)

Figure 7: Amplitude of the reflection coefficient (Amplitude (Γ), unit : dB) versus maximum displacement reached (D, unit : mm) with (points (B_i) $_{i=1,\dots,5}$, figure 5) or without (points (A_i) $_{i=1,\dots,5}$, figure 5) loading

Figure 8: Imaginary part of $\frac{\Gamma - \Gamma_{REF}}{\Gamma_{REF}}$ (no unit) versus maximum displacement reached (D_{MAX} , unit : mm) (from measures at the points (A_i) $_{i=1,\dots,5}$, figure 5)